

Spin As Scalar-Vector Information About Energy and Momentum?

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Newtonian mechanics (and traditional special relativity) focus on obtaining the following information: $x(t)$, p vector = $m_0 v(\text{vector}) / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0 cc^2 / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. We have argued in previous notes that as a next step one may examine $A = -Et + px$ (Lorentz invariant) to find degenerate A values for $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar / p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar / E$, where n is an integer.

In this note, we point out that E is a scalar and p a vector and so even though they are related numerically (E and the magnitude of p), one also has some information linked to the scalar-vector behaviour and we argue that this is the root of spin. In particular, to describe the vector-scalar relation, one needs a scalar product which includes E and p . Thus, we suggest that in finding spin one wishes to find as much information about the rotational-orientation link between E and p as possible.

This idea leads to different approaches for a particle with a rest mass and a photon, but both start with a scalar product of energy and momentum. In the case of a particle with rest mass, there is rest mass energy, $m_0 cc^2$, which is of an unknown nature and so one can only find a kind of orientational information between m_0 , E and p by linearizing $EE = pp + m_0 m_0$. In the case of a photon, $E = pc$ and so E and p are essentially the same thing, but one is a scalar and the other a vector. Again, one starts with a scalar inner product, but in this case one may investigate the link between the scalar nature of E and the vector nature of p directly because they are both essentially the same in the sense that there is no unknown m_0 (rest mass). Thus, one may consider two vectors whose cross product yields momentum density and whose separate dot products, energy density. We interpret the continuity equation from Maxwell's equations which uses the Poynting momentum as really an inner product of (p, E) , with one (p, E) written as a density and the second in terms of $p = -i \text{grad partial}$ and $E = i \text{d/dt partial}$.

Given that $A = -Et + px$ holds for both a particle with rest mass and a photon, this information should be incorporated in both scenarios and is as $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ appears for both descriptions. In other words, both descriptions make use of: $p = -i \text{grad partial}$ and $E = i \text{d/dt partial}$.

The Question of Information

We suggest that one needs to find as much information about a moving particle as possible. From Newtonian mechanics, one has the notion of energy E and momentum p (vector) for a free particle, but seems to only focus on the following information:

$$x(t), p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad \text{and} \quad E = m_0 cc^2 / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((1))$$

The latter two relativistic expressions yield the Newtonian results for $v/c \ll 1$. Although ((1)) provides necessary information for many situations, it does not provide all information available. In particular, we suggest that there are two other pieces of information (with experimental implications) which are ignored by ((1)).

-Et+px and Time-Spatial Resolutions

The first piece of missing information from Newtonian mechanics follows from:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

As argued in previous notes, A is degenerate for:

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

This leads to the quantum mechanical probability form: $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$.

Relationship Between the Scalar Nature of E and Vector Nature of p

The second piece of missing information, we suggest, is that of the relationship between a scalar E and a vector p. To consider this, one requires a scalar dot product involving the two dynamical quantities. Such a starting point holds both for a particle with rest mass m_0 and a photon. We suggest that the starting equation should be:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad \text{or} \quad E = pc \quad (\text{Photon}) \quad ((3))$$

At the same time, the result of ((2)) should be retained so we suggest that one also consider:

$$p = -i \text{grad} \quad \text{and} \quad E = i \partial / \partial t \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one wishes to investigate the scalar-vector relation between E and p. For a particle with rest mass, m_0 , energy is linked to m_0 which is essentially unknown in terms of its full properties. Thus, one may simply try to find an orientational relationship between m_0 and p by linearizing $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$.

This is the Dirac approach which leads to 4x4 matrices, i.e.

$$\{ B i \partial / \partial t + A \cdot (-i \text{grad} \partial) + I m_0 \} \exp(-iEt + ipx) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

B contains a 2x2 I (identity and -I along the diagonal and the three A matrices contain, $s(i)$ and $-s(i)$ (2x2 Pauli matrices) along the anti-diagonal. These 2x2 matrices act on 2 vectors, called spinors, which are linked to spin.

This whole strategy of linearizing, however, is an attempt to understand an orientational relation between E, p and m_0 which does not appear in the scalar equation: $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$. In other words, one is searching for extra information, in this case related to orientation between the scalar E and the vector p.

In the case of a photon, $E=pc$, yet one still needs orientational information and so we suggest a starting point of a scalar equation:

$$EE - pp = 0 \quad ((6))$$

In its present form ((6)) is not very useful because the root equation is $E=pc$. This root equation, however, shows that E and p are essentially the same (for $c=1$) except for the scalar versus vector behaviour. This suggests introducing two vectors E_i and B such that:

$$P \text{ density} = 1/u_0 \ E_i \times B \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad E \text{ density} = .5 \ e_0 \ E_i \text{ dot } E_i + .5/u_0 \ E_i \text{ dot } B \quad ((7b))$$

Note: $E = i \ d/dt$ and $p = -i \ \text{grad}$ so:

d/dt energy density + grad dot Poynting vector = 0 means that one has:

$$E (E \text{ density}) - p (p \text{ density}) = 0 \quad \text{which is } ((6)).$$

We consider E_i perpendicular to B and of the same magnitude ($c=1$) so $E_i \text{ dot } B$ need not be considered. We use these densities for one E, p set in ((6)) and $i d/dt, -\text{grad}$ for the other. Then, ((6)) as a quadratic equation carries more information than $E=pc$.

This approach leads to the well-known continuity equation using the Poynting momentum density from Maxwell's equations. We suggest here, however, that this equation is really ((6)) at its root and that one needs to keep information linked to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ from $A=-Et+px$, but at the same time find a relation between the scalar nature of E and the vector nature of p . This forces one to use densities.

As we have shown in previous notes, one may then linearize $EE - pp = 0$ to find:

$$i d/dt \text{ partial} (E_i + i B)_i + e_{ijk} (-d/dx_j \text{ partial}) (E_i + i B)_k = 0 \quad ((8))$$

E_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol is then the spin matrix i and one spin 1.

The main point we wish to make is that spin arises from trying to find an orientation relationship between the scalar E and vector p for a free particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics provides some dynamical information by giving $x(t)$ and $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Consider degeneracy of $A = -Et+px$ leads to the quantum $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which yields resolution in $t-x$ information. We suggest, however, that there is a third piece of information one may obtain, namely that following from analysing a relation between the orientation of the scalar E and vector p . This involves starting with a scalar dot product involving E and p for both the case of a particle with rest mass, m_0 , and a photon.

In the case of m_0 , one does not know its fundamental properties, so one may only consider its orientational relationship with E and p . In $EE = pp + m_0 m_0$, one simply has numbers, so to see orientation, one needs to linearize. This leads to the 4x4 Dirac matrices containing 2x2 Pauli matrices and the notion of spin .5.

For a photon, $E=pc$ and so E and p are essentially the same except that one is a scalar and the other a vector for $c=1$. One still needs a dot product, so we use: $EE - pp = 0$. This, however, contains the same information as $E=pc$ unless one treats E , p in two different ways. We suggest that one E , p set be represented by $i\partial/\partial t$ partial, $-\text{grad}$ partial and the second, by a density which explicitly shows the emergence of the scalar-vector forms of E , p . Thus, we suggest that p density = $1/\mu_0 E \times B$ (E and B perpendicular) and energy density = $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$. This leads to the usual continuity equation with the Poynting momentum density of Maxwell theory, but we suggest that its origins are $EE - pp = 0$ and $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-\text{grad}$ following from $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which follows from $A=-Et+px$ and degenerates. Linearizing $E \cdot E + B \cdot B$ then leads to e_{ijk} as a spin matrix and spin 1.